

**RELATIONSHIP NATURAL AND SCIENTIFIC EDUCATION WITH
ARTISTIC AND AESTHETIC EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS.**

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artistic and aesthetic development, creative abilities, self-realization.

Ключевые слова.

художественно-эстетическое развитие, творческие способности, самореализация.

"Artistic and aesthetic development" includes familiarizing children with art, the aesthetics of the developing environment, visual activities (drawing, modeling, appliqué), design and manual labor, musical education, cultural and leisure activities.

We most optimally carry out the implementation of the tasks of artistic and aesthetic development under the following conditions.

- Maximum consideration of the age and individual characteristics of children.
- The basis of artistic and aesthetic education is art and the surrounding life.
- The relationship of the artistic and creative activity of the children themselves with educational work, which provides a variety of food for the development of perception, figurative representations, imagination and creativity.
- Integration of various types of art and various types of artistic and creative activity, contributing to a deeper aesthetic understanding of reality, art and one's own artistic creativity; the formation of figurative representations, figurative, associative thinking and imagination.
- Respect for the results of children's creativity, the wide inclusion of their works in the life of a preschool educational institution.
- Organization of exhibitions, concerts, creation of an aesthetic developmental environment, etc.

- Variability of content, forms and methods of work with children in different areas of aesthetic education.

- Ensuring continuity in artistic and aesthetic education between all age groups of the kindergarten.

- Close relationship and interaction of the kindergarten with the family. Art, both classical and folk, is invaluable in aesthetic education. It should enter the life of children from an early age. In a preschool institution, works of art are used in three ways.

- Broad reliance on regional material, its specificity: nature, art - both classical and folk. Acquaintance with contemporary art and its creators working in the city, region. Children's knowledge of sights, their surroundings, significant events.

The first direction - art, including folk art, is included in the daily life of children as an integral part of the aesthetic environment. This is how music sounds in and out of the classroom, and works of fine art are used in the design of a preschool institution.

The second direction - art is the content of education: we introduce children to different types of art, to events, phenomena, objects revealed by artists, musicians, writers and poets in their works; with expressive means that allow you to create vivid images of reality.

The third direction - art is used in various types of artistic activity, serves the development of children's artistic creativity. Images of art are standards of beauty.

Introduction to art

Before the first visit to a museum or theater, teachers introduce the basic concepts of a particular type of art, and then - in an accessible form - tell children about what a portrait, painting, still life, landscape, easel is; arch, balcony; composer, architect, artist, poet, writer, singer, actor, performer, etc. Children are asked if they have been to a museum, theater, circus, exhibition; identify the range of their interests; determine what they would like to know, where to visit. This stage of work is carried out in the form of a conversation with a group of children, asking them questions: "Do you like to draw? What flower names do you know? What is the name of the profession of a person who composes poetry? Have you seen the puppet show in the theatre? Have you been to the museum, to the exhibition? And so on. Purposeful work on familiarization with art begins with the second younger group, but this does not mean that nothing was done in this area in the previous period: work on sensory development, familiarization with the outside world, fiction, music is, in fact, the preparatory stage of familiarization with art.

By the end of the third year of life, the child learns the basic ideas about color, size, shape; listens to fairy tales, memorizes nursery rhymes, learns to guess riddles, gets acquainted with the book and the rules for handling it, examines illustrations, learns to compare reality with its images in pictures, examines landscapes, together with the teacher remembers what he saw on a walk. We introduce children of this age to a folk toy, a toy - fun made of wood (pyramids, nesting dolls, bowls, Bogorodsk toys), we give the kids the opportunity to act with them (examine, disassemble, fold).

In the first junior group, kids are shown a puppet theater - first in the light, and then in the twilight. For the show, toys familiar to children are selected and mini-performances are played both based on fairy tales and on the basis of everyday situations. Gradually, children themselves are involved in the show: they are already able to provide all possible assistance to an adult.

The group arranges an exhibition of reproductions, folk toys, works of children of the preparatory group for school, that is, they begin to purposefully prepare the kids for visiting exhibitions, museums, theaters.

Exhibitions of children's works "How beautiful this world is, look", "Autumn has come to visit us", "Our city", etc. are constantly organized in the preschool institution. In addition, art activity corners are organized in groups.

Conditions (artistic environment) have been created for games, dramatization games, independent artistic activities of children with different types of materials, in which the educator is included as necessary.

Contact with art has a strong emotional inaction on the child. Usually, after a performance, visiting a museum, reading books, etc., children tend to imitate actors, singers, dancers, circus performers, etc. An adult must skillfully guide their actions so as not to extinguish interest, to support him. For this, it is expedient to organize games in ballet, puppet theater, etc., classes are held to enrich the knowledge of children in a particular artistic field, to develop visual, musical abilities.

Thus, familiarization with art in kindergarten begins at an early age and continues throughout preschool childhood.

The purpose of artistic education is the aesthetic and artistic development of preschool children.

The tasks of artistic education are the development of artistic perception, feelings and emotions, imagination, thinking, memory, speech: familiarization with elementary knowledge in the field of art; formation of interest in works of art;

development of children's creative abilities in various types of artistic, creativity;
formation of the foundations of the artistic and aesthetic culture of the individual.